

Russian Fisheries in the High North: Deterrence in the Grey Zone

Mariia Vladymyrova

To cite this article: Mariia Vladymyrova (19 Mar 2026): Russian Fisheries in the High North: Deterrence in the Grey Zone, The RUSI Journal, DOI: [10.1080/03071847.2026.2638132](https://doi.org/10.1080/03071847.2026.2638132)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03071847.2026.2638132>

© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 19 Mar 2026.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Russian Fisheries in the High North

Deterrence in the Grey Zone

Mariia Vladymyrova

Russian fishing fleets are engaged in covert and overt activities in the High North. Mariia Vladymyrova argues that they serve as instruments of strategic deterrence and coercive signalling. By leveraging ambiguity and dual-use capabilities, Russia blurs the line between civilian and military operations, complicating NATO's maritime situational awareness and demanding adaptive countermeasures in an evolving security environment.

On 19 September 2023, after a planned visit to Norway, the USS *Florida* – a nuclear-powered cruise-missile submarine of the US Navy – departed from Grøtsund harbour, just north of Tromsø. On its way towards the Barents Sea, the vessel was escorted by the Norwegian KV *Farm* patrol vessel and a tugboat of the Norwegian Coast Guard.¹ Around the same time, a Russian fishing trawler headed out to sea from the port of Tromsø.² Keeping about four nautical miles behind, the Russian trawler stayed on the submarine's course from Tromsø past Karlsøy and into the Barents Sea.

This might seem like a peculiar but harmless occurrence. However, such behaviour fits into a broader pattern. In December 2022, the Russian fishing trawler *Taurus* followed a similar course of action, passing near the USS *South Dakota* in Grøtsund harbour. An open-source investigation – led by the Norwegian state broadcaster NRK

and in partnership with several other Nordic news agencies – showed that these vessels tend to approach areas where US submarines surface in waters around Tromsø.

Since 2018, American submarines have increasingly surfaced near Tromsø for resupply during Arctic patrols, although this is not their sole purpose. The Barents Sea's shallow depths (up to 250 m) allow the US Navy to track the Russian Northern Fleet submarines departing Kola Bay. This early detection is possible in the so-called 'Bear Gap', a geo-strategic term for an area of water between North Cape, Bear Island and Svalbard. It is the point of entry from the Barents Sea to the deeper Norwegian Sea. If spotted in this area, a submarine can be monitored on its course towards the North Atlantic. This early detection opportunity is critical to maintain the Alliance's credible posture as the Russian Northern Fleet's nuclear-capable submarines have been

1. NRK, 'Amerikansk ubåt forlater Tromsø – med russisk tråler like bak' ['American Submarine Leaves Tromsø – With Russian Trawler Right Behind'], 19 September 2023, <https://www.nrk.no/tromsogfinnmark/amerikansk-ubåt-forlater-tromso_-med-russisk-traler-like-bak-1.16563828>, accessed 27 January 2026.
2. One of three Norwegian ports where Russian fishing vessels are still allowed to dock despite the comprehensive ban on port call issued against Russian-flagged vessels and vessels that flew the Russian flag as of 24 February 2022. See Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 'Norway Tightens Restrictions on Russian Fishing Vessels', press release, 10 June 2022, <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/tightens_restrictions/id2933272/>, accessed 27 January 2026.

intensifying their patrols in the North Atlantic over the past 10 years.³

The NRK-led investigation found that Russian fishing and research vessels had increasingly navigated in areas close to Norwegian military training sites, oil and gas fields and offshore wind farms. They had also mapped seabed infrastructure.⁴

Moreover, NRK reported, in 2021 and 2022, that the same Russian trawlers navigated in waters where damage to underwater infrastructure later occurred. In January 2022, a fibre-optic cable linking Svalbard to mainland Norway was disrupted, possibly due to sabotage. Prior to the incident, a Russian trawler, *Melkart-5*, had crossed the cable more than 107 times over a short period

in January.⁵ Earlier, in November 2021, Norway's Institute of Marine Research reported that about 4 km of a 60-km underwater cable at the Lofoten–Vesterålen Ocean Observatory had vanished.⁶ In both cases, the damaged cables were part of data collection and transmission networks. The cable to Svalbard carried sensitive data collected from satellite networks on Svalbard, and the 60-km cable carried data related to the seabed of the Lofoten and Vesterålen archipelagos. There has not yet been a definitive conclusion that these were malicious incidents.⁷ Although the strategic significance of these infrastructure sites is clear, the waters between these archipelagos in the Barents Sea are also busy fishing areas, where trawlers operate as part of their daily activities.

3. Astri Edvardsen and Birgitte Annie Hansen, “NATO Keeps a Close Watch Over Maritime Activity in the North,” Says COMSUBNATO, *High North News*, 12 November 2024, <<https://www.highnorthnews.com/en/nato-keeps-close-watch-over-maritime-activity-north-says-comsubnato>>, accessed 27 January 2026; Ellie Cook, ‘NATO Has a Russian Submarine Problem’, *Newsweek*, 13 May 2023, <<https://www.newsweek.com/nato-russia-submarines-nuclear-deterrent-ukraine-arctic-pacific-fleet-kola-peninsula-baltic-1798368>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
4. Beth Mørch Pettersen, ‘Fiskebåter og andre fartøy fra Russland kan drive spionasje og etterretning i Norge’ [‘From a Port in Northern Norway, a Suspected Russian Agent Boards the Fishing Trawler “Taurus”’], *NRK*, 19 April 2023, <<https://www.nrk.no/nordland/xl/fiskebater-og-andre-fartoy-fra-russland-kan-drive-spionasje-og-etterretning-i-norge-1.16371100>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
5. Beth Mørch Pettersen, Inghild Eriksen and Rune N Andreassen, ‘Den russiske fisketråleren “Melkart-5” krysser Svalbardfiberen over 140 ganger’ [‘One Russian Fishing Trawler Has Crossed Two Important Submarine Cables More Than 140 Times’], *NRK*, 8 October 2022, <<https://www.nrk.no/nordland/den-russiske-fisketråleren-melkart-5-krysser-svalbardfiberen-over-140-ganger-1.16128138>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
6. Benjamin Fredriksen et al., ‘Russiske trålere krysser kabler i Vesterålen og Svalbard før brudd’ [‘Russian Trawlers Crossed Cables in Vesterålen and Svalbard Before Rupture’], *NRK*, 26 June 2022, <<https://www.nrk.no/nordland/xl/russiske-tralere-krysser-kabler-i-vesteralen-og-svalbard-for-brudd-1.16007084>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
7. Håvard Gulldahl and Inghild Eriksen, ‘This is What the Damaged Svalbard Cable Looked Like When it Came Up from the Depths’, *NRK*, 26 May 2024, <<https://www.nrk.no/tromsogfinnmark/this-is-what-the-damaged-svalbard-cable-looked-like-when-it-came-up-from-the-depths-1.16895904>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

Russian Fisheries in the High North

Overall, there are 50 to 160 vessels of various types – including the Russian state-owned scientific research vessels – whose activities can be associated with the conduct of covert operations in the seas of the High North and the Northern Sea, as two major collaborative open-source journalistic investigations from the Nordics, the Netherlands and Belgium suggest.⁸ These vessels appear to have been fitted with advanced communications and surveillance equipment, including underwater sensors, not generally associated with the needs of fishing.⁹

The activity resembles the phenomenon of a ‘spy ship’ dating to the era of the Cold War. Then, fishing and research vessels were widely used for maritime surveillance and intelligence-gathering by the Soviet Union. One of the unclassified NATO Economic Committee working papers from 1977 underscored this activity: ‘Part of the Soviet fishing fleet is engaged in activities which have nothing to do with fishing; it is used as an extension of the Soviet Navy on specific military duties.’¹⁰

Between 2022 and 2024, a series of similar incidents occurred in the Baltic Sea. While the extent of damage varied – affecting both pipelines and cables – each incident carried an element of plausible deniability. This left open the question of whether it was deliberate sabotage of undersea energy and data infrastructure. These incidents have been largely seen in the context of a broader maritime threat environment shaped by the operations of Russia’s shadow fleet in the Baltic Sea.

The events made headlines across Europe and led NATO to strengthen its naval presence. The Alliance launched the Baltic Sentry patrolling mission in 2025. While this approach may be well-suited to the Baltic, where the geography – semi-enclosed coastline – allows for effective surveillance, its applicability to the High North and the Northern Sea is far less certain. While the operations of the shadow fleet are undeniably an imminent challenge – both in financing Russian military capabilities and posing grave environmental risks – the activities of the Russian fishing fleet warrant sustained analysis. The Russian threat at sea, relying on ‘dual-use assets’, is likely to persist

across oceans, and thus, to consider appropriate countermeasures, a nuanced understanding of the tactics at play is needed.

This article builds on the observation that, in some cases, these vessels exhibit overt operational patterns. For instance, as seen in the case of *Taurus*, they may either deliberately seek visibility or be indifferent to being observed – for example, by repeatedly and rapidly crossing over cables. Unlike clandestine intelligence-gathering operations, this article argues that the activities of Russian fishing vessels follow a clear deterrent rationale, serving as instruments of coercive signalling.

The idea of coercive signalling conducted by proxy may seem at odds with the clear threat communication that deterrence theorists emphasise. However, a closer examination of two key factors – the nature of deterrence operations at sea and Russian approaches to deterrence – is valuable. Such an examination provides valuable insights into why the use of the Russian fishing fleet – and, by extension, other non-naval vessels – for surveillance and alleged sabotage should be seen as part of a broader deterrence signalling effort targeting NATO member states.

First, the article outlines the distinctive features and functions of deterrence in the maritime domain. To contextualise this discussion, the article draws on key observations of Russia’s 2022 Maritime Doctrine. Building on this foundation, it then examines Russian approaches to deterrence, situating the discussed tactic within the broader concept of ‘strategic deterrence’. The utilisation of the civilian fleet for coercive signalling exemplifies the adaptability of Russian deterrence strategies, given the persistent gap between the country’s declared maritime ambitions and the capabilities of the Russian Navy. This adaptation incorporates activities typically associated with the grey zone into the broader framework of Russia’s strategic deterrence. The article concludes by examining how this tactic of coercive signalling aligns with Moscow’s longstanding strategic objectives in the Arctic and its anticipation of geostrategic shifts in the High North following Sweden’s and Finland’s accession to NATO, amid Moscow’s ongoing aggression against Ukraine.

8. Sunniva Grimstad Hestenes and Monica White Martinsen, ‘265 russarar har løyve til å segle fritt langs norskekysten: – Noreg har vore naive’ [‘265 Russians Have Permission to Sail Freely along the Norwegian Coast: Norway Has Been Naive’], *NRK*, 21 April 2023, <https://www.nrk.no/nordland/russiske-skip-treng-ikkje-los-om-bord-_grunn-til-a-vere-bekymra-meiner-forskar-1.16377927>, accessed 27 January 2026.

9. *Ibid.*

10. North Atlantic Council, ‘The Soviet Fishing Industry’, North Atlantic Council Economic Committee Working Paper, AC/127-WP/503, 11 March 1977. Also see Marc J Berkowitz, ‘Soviet Naval Spetsnaz Forces’, *Naval War College Review* (Vol. 41, No. 2, Spring 1988), pp. 5–21.

Naval Shadowing: Posturing and Surveillance

From the viewpoint of naval strategy, the activities of Russian fishing vessels resemble what is termed ‘shadowing’ or ‘trailing’.¹¹ ‘Shadowing’ is part of naval routine to such an extent that elaborated definitions are rare; however, the term is often used in naval parlance and doctrinal documents.¹² The practice entails naval forces following a foreign vessel – typically a warship or submarine – within, or in proximity to, their territorial waters at a safe distance to monitor its activities and maintain contact. While shadowing can be for surveillance and intelligence gathering, or the denial of these activities to adversaries, shadowing is rarely a covert manoeuvre; its purpose is to signal one’s presence.¹³

To deter adversaries, showcase capabilities and assert control over the claimed territorial sea and adjacent waters, states frequently employ this tactic in waters of heightened tensions. For instance, China has routinely shadowed US and Philippine warships and other foreign state vessels in the South China Sea since 2015.¹⁴ The Russian Navy frequently shadowed NATO exercises and member states’ warships on its passages in the Black Sea before the 2022 full-scale invasion of Ukraine.¹⁵ For their part, with a notable increase since 2014, the navies of NATO member states have consistently engaged in shadowing Russian naval and research vessels in the Northern and Baltic Seas, as well as the Arctic.¹⁶

These instances of shadowing are illustrative in two major aspects. First, they reveal the growing apprehension of North Atlantic coastal states towards the threat potential of the Russian-

flagged vessels, even though they are formally research vessels. Second, and more importantly, the shadowing action speaks to what deterrence at sea is fundamentally about – presence.

What sets the described case of *Taurus* and other fishing vessels apart is that these are not vessels on naval duty shadowing NATO warships and submarines. Employing a civilian fleet in such a way indicates a shift in Russia’s naval strategy: civilian vessels are now being used for pursuing national interests. The dual-use of the Russian fishing fleet strongly resembles China’s use of fishing fleets in the South China Sea since 2009. There, they are used for intelligence gathering, and designating and enforcing territorial claims.¹⁷ While the Chinese case has been in analytical focus for a while, the activities of the Russian fishing fleet in the High North and North Atlantic have received little sustained analysis.

Deterrence At Sea

The use of civilian vessels for strategic purposes capitalises on plausible deniability. It allows a state to engage in malign activities against an adversary without triggering direct confrontation.¹⁸ While below-the-threshold operations thrive on ambiguity, deterrence is often said to rely on clarity. At its core, deterrence aims to shape an adversary’s decision-making by increasing the perceived costs and risks of a particular course of action. The credibility of a threat depends on whether the adversary perceives it as believable. This, in turn, requires that the threatened response is both clearly communicated and backed by capability and commitment – an equation known as the ‘three Cs’ of deterrence. In practice, credibility

-
11. Edward Hampshire, ‘From Malin Head to “Okean 75”: Shadowing and Intelligence Collection Operations by Royal Navy Surface Ships 1975–1985’, *Intelligence and National Security* (Vol. 33, No. 5, 2018), pp. 659–74.
 12. For example, see HM Government, *The UK National Strategy for Maritime Security*, CP 724 (London: The Stationery Office, 2022).
 13. Hampshire, ‘From Malin Head to “Okean 75”’.
 14. Micah McCartney, ‘Pictures Show Chinese Warships Shadowing US and Ally in South China Sea’, *Newsweek*, 4 January 2024; Dzirhan Mahadzir, ‘Chinese Warships Shadow Canadian, U.S., Japanese Warships in East China Sea, the Philippines Resupply Second Thomas Shoal’, *USNI News*, 8 September 2023, <<https://news.usni.org/2023/09/08/chinese-warships-shadow-canadian-u-s-japanese-warships-in-east-china-sea-the-philippines-resupply-second-thomas-shoal>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
 15. Nancy A Youssef, ‘Putin Dispatches Russian Vessels to Shadow U.S. Warships During Flare-Up’, *Wall Street Journal*, 20 November 2021; Murray Brewster, ‘Russian Forces Tested NATO’s “Resolve” During Recent Black Sea Exercises, Says Canadian Commander’, *CBC News*, 31 July 2019.
 16. Andrew Salerno-Garthwaite, ‘HMS Richmond Shadows Russian Warship Through English Channel’, *Naval Technology*, 9 November 2023, <<https://www.naval-technology.com/news/hms-richmond-shadows-russian-warship-through-english-channel/>>, accessed 27 January 2026; Thomas Nilsen, ‘NATO Frigates Shadow Kuznetsov Battle Group Heading North’, *Barents Observer*, 30 January 2017, <<https://thebarentsobserver.com/en/security/2017/01/nato-frigates-shadow-kuznetov-battle-group-heading-north>>, accessed 27 January 2026; Tim Hopher, ‘Baltic Military Shadow-Boxing Said to Reach Cold War Levels’, *Reuters*, 4 May 2015.
 17. Ryan Martinson, ‘Catching Sovereignty Fish: Chinese Fishers in the Southern Spratlys’, *Marine Policy* (Vol. 125, 2021), pp. 1–11. See also Rob McLaughlin, ‘The Law of the Sea and PRC Gray-Zone Operations in the South China Sea’, *American Journal of International Law* (Vol. 116, No. 4, 2022), pp. 821–35.
 18. Christian Bueger and Timothy Edmunds, *Understanding Maritime Security* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024), pp. 67–70.

is established through coercive signalling, which involves both statements and actions designed to convey their commitments and to threaten costs and/or risks of non-compliance to adversaries.

The functions of ambiguity in deterrence remain debated. For a threat to be credible, uncertainty is never purely eliminated. A threat often hinges on the same manipulation of escalation risks that grey-zone tactics exploit.¹⁹ An actor may deliberately cultivate the fear of escalation as a tool for coercive leverage, even while keeping operations below the threshold of a military response.

The extent of uncertainty necessary for achieving credible deterrence can be further refined by distinguishing between general and immediate deterrence. Immediate deterrence requires unambiguous signalling due to the urgency of the crisis, as the adversary must clearly perceive the threatened response. General deterrence, by contrast, does not necessitate such direct signalling. Instead, it relies on instilling a general sense of risk in a potential adversary, ensuring that active hostilities are never seriously considered in a relationship that is tense but not in acute crisis.²⁰

Lawrence Freedman highlights that the key distinction lies in the degree of strategic engagement. For general deterrence to be credible, it depends largely on the deterred party's assessment of its broader strategic environment rather than of immediate threats. It functions by fostering an understanding of the vital interests of the party conducting the deterrence – interests that the deterred party recognises must be respected to avoid escalation.²¹

Due to the distinctive qualities of the maritime domain – particularly the stealth and mobility it affords – naval power is inherently more suited to achieving general deterrence. Naval forces can operate with flexibility far from their country's ports, and their ability to swiftly reposition introduces uncertainty to an adversary's strategic calculations.²² Historically, that has been a

defining feature of naval strategy. More recently, it is most prominently exemplified by the strategic use of nuclear-powered and nuclear-capable submarines, as stealth and survivable platforms, which serve as key guarantees of second- and third-strike capabilities in nuclear deterrence.

While the deployment of naval power to signal commitment in situations of immediate deterrence may exacerbate tensions, as some studies suggest, in practice, it primarily serves as an instrument of general deterrence.²³ The image of credibility here relies on naval presence: forces that are physically deployed at sea, capable of accomplishing maritime situational awareness in their own territorial sea and beyond, and, if necessary, prepared to intervene with force if a crisis arises.²⁴ This presence reinforces a persistent background threat that shapes the adversary's perception of the strategic environment in a way that favours the deterring party's objectives. Much like the concept of 'boots on the ground', it acts as the symbolic embodiment of a deterrence commitment; at sea, this commitment is embodied by the presence of naval vessels.²⁵

On this, deterrence at sea is about preventing immediate escalation.

The potential for rapid and stealthy redeployment, along with the enhancement of an actor's posture elsewhere, introduces an element of uncertainty that is central to the credibility of a general sea-based deterrent. On this, deterrence at sea is about preventing immediate escalation. But it is also about continuously shaping the strategic environment and establishing control in contested waters. Against this backdrop, a shadowing manoeuvre – the basic tenet of the exercise of deterrence at sea – if accomplished by proxy, could reinforce uncertainty, and, in

19. Thomas C Schelling, *The Strategy of Conflict* (London: Pickle Partners Publishing, 2015), pp. 217–38; Patrick M Morgan, *Deterrence Now* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003), pp. 105–15. See also Brett V Benson, *Constructing International Security: Alliances, Deterrence, and Moral Hazard* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012); Timothy W Crawford, *Pivotal Deterrence: Third-Party Statecraft and the Pursuit of Peace* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2003).

20. See Morgan, *Deterrence Now*, pp. 80–115.

21. Lawrence Freedman, 'General Deterrence and the Balance of Power', *Review of International Studies* (Vol. 15, No. 2, 1989), pp. 199–210.

22. Alexander L George and Richard Smoke, *Deterrence in American Foreign Policy: Theory and Practice* (New York, NY: Columbia University Press, 1974), p. 1.

23. Erik Gartzke and Jon R Lindsay, *Elements of Deterrence: Strategy, Technology, and Complexity in Global Politics* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2024), pp. 224–51.

24. Raymond Cohen, "'Where Are the Aircraft Carriers?': Nonverbal Communication in International Politics", *Review of International Studies* (Vol. 7, No. 2, 1981), pp. 79–90.

25. Maria Mälksoo, 'NATO's New Front: Deterrence Moves Eastward', *International Affairs* (Vol. 100, No. 2, 2024), pp. 531–47.

this logic, the overall credibility of the deterrent posture at sea.

To borrow a concept from classic sea power theory, the Russian fishing fleet – by occasionally demonstrating its alleged dual-use capabilities – becomes the Russian Navy’s ‘fleet-in-being’. Through covert-to-overt operational patterns, these vessels signal the capability to function as a covert extension of Russian naval power, threatening to devastate vital maritime seabed connectivity and other offshore assets of the targeted NATO member states. This signalling tactic shifts coercive signalling to the grey zone and reinforces Russia’s general deterrence posture at sea. This tactic operationalises the uncertainty and compels the targeted actors to tie up the limited naval capabilities for enhanced surveillance and patrolling. These implications are well-appreciated by Moscow: this tactic, in fact, aligns with both the Russian concept of ‘strategic deterrence’, and has been institutionalised by several provisions of the 2022 iteration of the Maritime Doctrine.

The 2022 Maritime Doctrine: Strategic Adaptation in the High North and Implications for Deterrence Posture

To contextualise Russian perceptions of the current maritime strategic environment and to pin down why Moscow engages in shadowing by proxy against NATO vessels in the High North, this article analyses the 2022 Maritime Doctrine (hereafter, the Doctrine) issued on 31 July 2022. The present study does not examine the Doctrine comprehensively. Instead, it focuses on how the Doctrine reflects the Russian perceptions of the geostrategic environment in the High North,

and proceeds by focusing on a major novelty introduced by the Doctrine: the provisions on ‘mobilization readiness and preparedness in maritime activities’. It concludes by connecting these aspects of the Doctrine to more general conceptualisations of Russian approaches to deterrence, also known as the concept of ‘strategic deterrence’.

The 2022 Doctrine is an updated Russian strategic planning document that complements and refines the state’s National Security Strategy from August 2021 for the maritime domain.²⁶ The peculiarity of the Doctrine is that naval activities are presented along with other dimensions of maritime policy, for instance, environmental and resource management, shipbuilding and research.²⁷ These provisions institutionalise the employment of civilian fleets and maritime infrastructure as dual-use assets to sustain Russia’s military-strategic objectives across oceans.

An important aspect to consider is that the Doctrine was the first high-level policy document articulating Russia’s broader strategic priorities in the aftermath of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine. The Doctrine must have been under development before the war. However, the initial failure of the invasion drastically altered the geopolitical landscape from what the Russian government had envisioned.²⁸ Rather than paving the way to renegotiate a ‘multipolar’ world order aligned with the Russian political leadership’s aspirations, the full-scale invasion of Ukraine resulted in NATO’s consolidation. This development particularly affected the northern flank of the Alliance, evidenced by the accession of Finland and Sweden, and led to a major geostrategic shift: deepening connectivity of the military infrastructure of the member states in Northern Europe.²⁹ Thus, Moscow’s primary strategic deterrent forces of the Northern Fleet on the Kola Peninsula and further along the Arctic coast of Siberia, while

26. What distinguishes Russian naval strategy-making is that the document goes beyond simply delineating the role and applications of naval power. Instead, the Doctrine encompasses a range of objectives covering maritime security policy, environmental policy and matters related to international maritime shipping. All these objectives are consolidated under the umbrella of ‘national maritime policy’, which provides a clear picture of the Kremlin’s ambitions at sea. See Russian Federation, ‘The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation’, approved by Presidential Decree No. 512, 31 July 2022, <<http://www.kremlin.ru/acts/bank/48215>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

27. See Michael Kofman, ‘Evolution of Russian Naval Strategy’, in Andrew Monaghan and Richard Connolly (eds), *The Sea in Russian Strategy* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2022), pp. 100–03.

28. On the morning of 26 February 2022, one of the main Russian state news agencies, *RIA Novosti*, published the article ‘The Rise of Russia and the New World’. The publication was pre-set and demonstrates the ambition of the Russian military and political leadership to capture Ukraine in two days. The article claimed that Western global domination could be considered completely and finally over. The publication was deleted the same day, but its archive copy can still be assessed. See Petr Akopov, ‘Nastuplenie Rossii i Novogo Mira’ [‘The Rise of Russia and the New World’], *RIA Novosti*, 26 February 2022, available in the Wayback Machine, <<https://web.archive.org/web/20220226051154/https://ria.ru/20220226/rossiya-1775162336.html>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

29. Karsten Friis and Rolf Tamnes, ‘The Defence of Northern Europe: New Opportunities, Significant Challenges’, *International Affairs* (Vol. 100, No. 2, March 2024), pp. 813–24.

not affected by the demands of the war against Ukraine, became increasingly exposed.³⁰

Furthermore, the tightening grip of sanctions resulted in the cessation of significant multilateral scientific, energy and logistic cooperation projects. As a result, only a handful of bilateral frameworks remain between Russia and its Western neighbours in the High North. These are primarily focused on border cooperation, rescue operations and fisheries management. Despite Moscow's deepening links with Beijing, primarily in energy and infrastructure projects, the limited bilateral cooperation with the West in the High North remains important. These frameworks offer scarce opportunities for enhancing Russia's situational awareness in the region.³¹

The Arctic is identified as the 'vital' priority, along with Russia's internal waters and territorial seas.

The Doctrine reflects this shift through a change in regional priorities. The Arctic is identified as the 'vital' priority, along with Russia's internal waters and territorial seas. Here, the Doctrine recognises that 'the Arctic's transformation into a region of global competition extends beyond economic considerations to encompass military dimensions as well'.³² This competition is exacerbated by 'efforts by a number of states to weaken the Russian Federation's control over the Northern Sea Route [NSR], a build-up of foreign naval presence in the Arctic, and an increase in conflict potential in this region', and thus compels Moscow to 'establish control over naval

activities of foreign states in the waters of the NSR' to secure its own interests in the region.³³ This prioritisation is backed by commitments to bolster the capabilities of the Northern and Pacific fleets.³⁴ These fleets are key to maintaining the NSR whose further development into a year-round operational shipping line is set as a major priority.

The formal separation of the Arctic and the Atlantic in the Doctrine belies the strategic and military convergence of these two dimensions in the European High North.³⁵ The strategic perception of the European High North is shaped by Russia's characteristic rhetoric of 'encirclement by NATO'. The Doctrine unambiguously identifies 'the expansion of NATO's military infrastructure toward Russia's borders and the increasing number of exercises in seas adjacent to Russian territory' as a threat.³⁶ It expresses concern over what is described as 'a continuous deterrent effort by the U.S. and its allies against Russia', exerting 'economic, political, legal, informational, and military pressure on the Russian Federation to discredit and reduce the effectiveness of its maritime activities'.³⁷ In response, the Doctrine emphasises 'strategic and regional deterrence of potential adversaries, and preventing aggression against the Russian Federation from oceanic and maritime directions' as a strategic objective.³⁸

This objective is particularly reflected in Russia's ambition to achieve circumpolar sea control in its coastal waters and along the NSR, and to project force into regional navigational chokepoints – such as the Greenland–Iceland–UK and Greenland–Iceland–Norway gaps, as well as the Svalbard archipelago.³⁹ At the same time, the Russian Navy operates under persistent modernisation constraints, which affects, in particular, its surface naval capability and

30. Sidharth Kaushal et al., *The Balance of Power Between Russia and NATO in the Arctic and High North*, RUSI Whitehall Paper, Vol. 100 (Abingdon: Routledge, 2022), pp. 6–14.

31. Despite Russian aggression against Ukraine in 2014, a degree of cooperation and coordination between Russia and NATO member states persisted in the European High North. Dialogue and joint initiatives on issues such as environmental conservation and search and rescue operations were driven by shared interests in maintaining regional stability, environmental security and resource management.

32. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 50.

33. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 22 (8) and Article 50 (6).

34. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 14 (3).

35. This convergence is particularly present in operational terms, attributable to the positioning of Russia's major sea-based strategic deterrent on the Kola Peninsula, bordering the Barents Sea. Recent actions by the Russian government, including the modernisation of the Northern Fleet Command into Joint Strategic Command North, with plans for further development as one of Russia's five military districts, suggest a trajectory towards heightened military presence in the region. See Mathieu Boulègue, *The Militarization of Russian Polar Politics*, Chatham House Research Paper (London: Chatham House, 2022).

36. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 22 (4).

37. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 20.

38. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 28 (4). See also Sidharth Kaushal and René Balletta, 'An Asymmetric Approach to the Use of Maritime Forces in Competing with Russia', *RUSI Occasional Papers* (February 2024), pp. 10–13.

39. Boulègue, *The Militarization of Russian Polar Politics*.

complicates Russia's ability to effectively translate its ambitious pursuits into tangible outcomes.⁴⁰ The Northern and Pacific Fleets, despite all declared resource allocation, in their present condition may face capability overstretch if navigating between the North Atlantic, the Arctic and the NSR.⁴¹

It is worth noting that the Doctrine reflects Moscow's pretence of a cooperative stance in the Arctic, even though it has practically ceased its participation in the Arctic Council in the past three years.⁴² Despite this fact, Moscow aims to engage more with 'friendly countries' – a colloquial reference to non-Western states used in Russian foreign policy discourse – in economic and research development projects.⁴³ In the European High North, Greenland and the Faroe Islands may be considered by the Russian political leadership – to some extent – as 'friendly', too. Unlike Denmark, Norway or the UK, these autonomous polities are not included in the 'unfriendly states and territories' list. This suggests that Russia's leadership may seek opportunities for bilateral cooperation with these polities in the maritime domain, first and foremost, in fisheries management and logistics.⁴⁴

The Doctrine presents somewhat contradictory aims: it emphasises sea control in the High North and deterrent effort against NATO to assert Russian maritime claims, while simultaneously seeking to maintain a cooperative stance, key for the further build-up of energy and logistics within the NSR. Thus, Russia is compelled to adapt its approach to asserting its claims in the waters of the High North. The use of non-military capabilities is key to the adaptation of the deterrent maritime posture. It further reflects Moscow's recognition of the limitations of its naval capabilities. Rather than relying solely on conventional military power projection, Russia merges grey-zone tactics to shape the strategic environment and advance

its general deterrent posture to the High North. The shift into grey-zone tactics allows Russia to maintain a pretence of cooperative engagement, and deny that it is engaging in a military build-up and adopting an offensive posture in the Arctic.

This observation is supported by a chapter in the Doctrine on 'mobilization preparation and mobilization readiness'.⁴⁵ The chapter prescribes measures for preparatory training and mobilisation readiness of crews operating civilian vessels. It further provides for their subsequent transfer into operation under the command of the Russian Armed Forces in the case of imminent threat or wartime, the so-called 'recall system'.⁴⁶ Key priorities include refining the regulatory framework to implement the recall system for Russian-flagged vessels and implementing measures to increase the number of ships sailing under the Russian flag.⁴⁷ Furthermore, the Doctrine makes it possible to 'conscript' transport, fishing and other specialised vessels as well as port facilities into the operation of the Russian Armed Forces. It also enables 'other troops, military formations, and special operations forces' to conduct 'special operations' during peacetime.⁴⁸ To facilitate these measures, the Doctrine sets an objective to promptly upgrade civilian vessels with means respective to their designated wartime roles.⁴⁹

The focus on the mobilisation preparedness of civilian fleets aims to enhance the Russian Navy's adaptability. At the same time, it also establishes legal conditions to institutionalise the factual dual-use condition of the critical maritime infrastructure, including both civilian fleets and the infrastructure in the High North.⁵⁰

This article makes the case for framing Russia's use of civilian fishing vessels as a coercive signalling action. Doing so better captures the Russian practice of deterrence with non-military means in the maritime domain. In essence,

40. Igor Delanoë, 'The Russian Navy and the Arctic: A New Reality, Old Challenges', *Hot Takes*, blog of the Network for Strategic Analysis, 23 August 2023, <<https://ras-nsa.ca/the-russian-navy-and-the-arctic-a-new-reality-old-challenges/>>, accessed 27 January 2026. See also Nick Childs, 'Russia's New Maritime Doctrine: Adrift from Reality?', *Military Balance* blog, 2 September 2022, <<https://www.iiss.org/online-analysis/military-balance/2022/09/russias-new-maritime-doctrine-adrift-from-reality/>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

41. Delanoë, 'The Russian Navy and the Arctic'.

42. Elizabeth Buchanan, *Red Arctic: Russian Strategy Under Putin* (Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press, 2023), pp. 151–53.

43. Astri Edvardsen, 'Massive Russian Mobilization in the Arctic, High North News' Overview Shows', *High North News*, 1 September 2023, <<https://www.highnorthnews.com/en/massive-russian-mobilization-arctic-high-north-news-overview-shows/>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

44. Government of the Russian Federation, 'Order No. 430-r: List of Foreign States and Territories Committing Unfriendly Actions Against the Russian Federation, Russian Legal Entities, and Individuals', 5 March 2022, <<http://government.ru/news/44745/>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

45. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Chapter VIII, Articles 83–85.

46. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 84.

47. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Articles 85 (1) and (3).

48. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 85 (9).

49. Russian Federation, 'The Maritime Doctrine of the Russian Federation', Article 86 (5).

50. See House of Lords, International Relations and Defence Committee, 'Our Friends in the North: UK Strategy Towards the Arctic', HL Paper 8, 1st Report of Session 2023–24, 29 November 2023, pp. 27–31.

‘strategic deterrence’ is a concept of Russian deterrence theory and describes a strategy that operates with both soft and hard instruments of power. It is characterised by merging nuclear, non-nuclear and non-military elements, across various domains. This happens both regionally and globally, throughout all phases of interaction in times of peace and war.⁵¹ This holistic presentation highlights what is described as the three main features of Russia’s strategic deterrence concept: its universality; its continuousness; and its combination of deterrent and coercive logic.⁵² In this context, enforcing uncertainty on an adversary serves as both an incremental element to the employed tactics and as an objective that facilitates Russian strategic deterrence. Ultimately, Russia’s approach to deterrence as a strategy aims to shape the adversarial perceptions of the strategic environment, rather than leveraging concrete threat scenarios. This aligns with the Western concept of general deterrence that is discussed above.

Dima Adamsky and Kristin Ven Bruusgaard observe that the integration of non-military means is incremental to the Russian concept of ‘strategic deterrence’. However, further empirical refinement is needed to better define these non-military means and the respective consideration and tactics motivating their use.⁵³ The following sections elaborate on how the case for employment of the Russian fishing fleet in the High North can be considered as evidence of Russia’s evolving approaches to deterrence in the grey zone. It concludes by observing that this is shaping the strategic environment in line with the objectives of Russian general deterrent posture.

Unpacking Russia’s Grey Zone Deterrence in the High North

The employment of the fishing fleet for strategic purposes has two main features. First, permissive maritime legal regimes allow fishing fleets to be ever-present, including the operation of these vessels in ports of NATO member states. This is despite comprehensive restrictions in the aftermath of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022. Second, for the covert-to-overt pattern

of action. These vessels perform covert tasks of surveillance and may be utilised for sabotage of maritime infrastructure or preparation thereof, while occasionally engaging in overt deterrent action like shadowing. Although tensions may arise in the execution of this approach, the sequence of these actions reinforces this tactic as a signal for the targeted audiences, namely the military and political authorities of NATO coastal states.

The Russian fishing vessels demonstrate certain capabilities. They engage in suspicious navigation, going dark or deliberately spoofing AIS (automatic identification system). At the same time, the exact intent, capability and the proxy relationship to the Navy, or any other state service, remains plausibly deniable and uncertain. It remains so until an incident is investigated on a case-by-case basis. This enhances the strategic ambiguity on the extent of Russian naval and grey-zone capabilities in general, especially considering the mounting cases of various incidents of alleged shadowing, surveillance and sabotage action.

This effect is further reinforced by the framing within Russia’s evolving doctrinal developments. This both signals intent and elevates the perceived threat potential associated with Russian fishing vessels. Thus, there is uncertainty over what assets are at the disposal of the Russian Navy – its officially commissioned fleet – and further uncertainty over whether the civilian assets are a ‘fleet-in-being’ operating in the grey zone. This seems to accomplish a sense of ‘a threat which leaves something to chance’, as Thomas Schelling described it in his authoritative work on nuclear bargaining.⁵⁴ By making attribution difficult and keeping operational patterns ambiguous, these vessels contribute to the Russian deterrent posture by blurring maritime situational awareness and complicating responses and threat scenario-building for NATO states’ navies in the European High North, Baltic Sea and North Atlantic.

The recent incidents in the High North – including the damage to the Lofoten–Vesterålen underwater monitoring cable, the Svalbard data cable, the Shetland data cable and the series of incidents in the Baltic Sea – have greatly increased concerns over the extent of Russian naval

51. Dmitry (Dima) Adamsky, *The Russian Way of Deterrence: Strategic Culture, Coercion, and War*, 1st edition (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2024), pp. 124–26.

52. Kristin Ven Bruusgaard, ‘Russian Strategic Deterrence’, *Survival* (Vol. 58, No. 4, 2016), pp. 7–26.

53. Dmitry Adamsky, ‘Deterrence à la Ruse: Its Uniqueness, Sources and Implications’, in Frans Osinga and Tim Sweijts (eds), *NL ARMS Netherlands Annual Review of Military Studies: Deterrence in the 21st Century – Insights from Theory and Practice* (Breda: Springer, 2021), pp. 161–75; Ven Bruusgaard, ‘Russian Strategic Deterrence’.

54. Thomas C Schelling, *Arms and Influence* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2020), pp. 101–22.

capabilities.⁵⁵ The most recent Russian treatise, in line with Russian studies of deterrence, sees this tactic's features as an escalatory move: 'severing submarine cables in the Baltic Sea at first and then in the Atlantic, preceding such actions with a public demonstration of Russia's military-technical capabilities for such operations'.⁵⁶ While none of the incidents has been definitively linked to Russian state involvement, they highlight the vulnerability of seabed infrastructure, even to relatively simple interference.⁵⁷ The incidents impose a significant cost and burden on NATO forces. The Alliance can only deploy limited naval capabilities and these are already engaged in the Baltic Sea and undertaking enhanced patrolling. NATO forces continue to face the pressure to monitor and protect both the offshore and seabed infrastructure that is vital for energy supplies and communication networks in the Northern Sea and beyond.⁵⁸

Another tactic for operationalising uncertainty involves exploiting the potential escalation resulting from the threat of force when jurisdiction over maritime areas is contested, as well as through law enforcement actions targeting fishing vessels. These shadowing civilian vessels exploit legal regimes of international navigation. On the one hand, these may seem more permissive for civilian vessels. Despite the sanctions, Russian fishing vessels enjoy unrestricted access in the waters of the High North beyond Russian coastal jurisdiction, and are still allowed to dock in three ports in the north of Norway and enjoy restricted

access to the ports of the Faroe Islands.⁵⁹ On the other hand, commercial vessels do not enjoy the sovereign immunity afforded to a warship.⁶⁰ This means that in territorial waters and exclusive economic zones (EEZs), a commercial vessel can be boarded, inspected and seized by an enforcing state if certain conditions are satisfied. Yet, so far, NATO member states have diverging national interpretations of the respective provisions of the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea.

This issue is pressing in Svalbard, for example, due to Russia's persistent disagreement with Norway on coastal jurisdiction in maritime zones.⁶¹ For example, in 2005, the Russian trawler *Elektron* evaded arrest by the Norwegian Coast Guard for alleged illegal fishing in the Fisheries Protection Zone of the Svalbard archipelago. Despite two Norwegian Coast Guard inspectors on board, the trawler fled towards Russian territorial waters, while pursued by Norwegian Coast Guard ships and helicopters. Norway approached the incident with a high degree of caution. Both parties ultimately contained the dispute's potential escalation by treating it as a violation of states' sovereign immunity in matters of flag jurisdiction and resolving it through bilateral negotiations.⁶² Moreover, the risk of accidental collision involving a civilian vessel persists due to military exercises of both NATO member states and Russia.⁶³ As a recent study put it, 'while the possibility of an armed conflict in Svalbard's waters may be deemed low, one misplaced fishing trawler might serve as a dangerous trigger if seized by another

-
55. Lisbeth Kirk, 'Mysterious Atlantic Cable Cuts Linked to Russian Fishing Vessels', *EUObserver*, 26 October 2022, <<https://euobserver.com/nordics/156342>>, accessed 27 January 2026; *BBC News*, 'Damaged Cable Leaves Shetland Cut Off from Mainland', 20 October 2022; Niels Nagelhus Schia and Ida Rødningen, 'The Subsea Cable Cut at Svalbard January 2022: What Happened, What Were the Consequences, and How Were They Managed?', NUPI Policy Brief, 2023, <<https://www.nupi.no/en/publications/cristin-pub/the-subsea-cable-cut-at-svalbard-january-2022-what-happened-what-were-the-consequences-and-how-were-they-managed>>, accessed 27 January 2026; Rickard Lindholm, 'Mapping Undersea Infrastructure Attacks in the Baltic Sea', Wilson Center, 24 March 2025, <<https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/mapping-undersea-infrastructure-attacks-baltic-sea>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
56. Dmitrii Vital'evich Trenin, Sergei Aleksandrovich Karaganov and Sergei Iosifovich Avakyants, *Ot sderzhivaniya k ustrasheniyu. Yadernoe oruzhie, geopolitika, koalitsionnaya strategiya [From Containment to Deterrence: Nuclear Weapons, Geopolitics, Coalition-Making Strategy]* (Moscow: Molodaya gvardiya, 2024).
57. Runar Spansvoll, 'Studying Moscow's Coercive Campaign Against Norway', *RUSI Journal* (Vol. 168, No. 3, 2023), pp. 74–85.
58. Christian Bueger and Tobias Liebetrau, 'Critical Maritime Infrastructure Protection: What's the Trouble?', *Marine Policy* (Vol. 155, 2023).
59. Olav Schram Stokke, 'External Shocks, Resilience and Barents Sea Fisher Compliance', in Olav Schram Stokke, Andreas Østhagen, Andreas Raspotnik (eds), *Marine Resources, Climate Change and International Management Regimes* (London: Bloomsbury, 2022); Astri Edvardsen and Birgitte Annie Hansen, 'The Faroe Island and Russia Reached a Fisheries Agreement for 2025', *High North News*, 2 December 2024, <<https://www.highnorthnews.com/en/faroe-island-and-russia-reached-fisheries-agreement-2025>>, accessed 27 January 2026.
60. 'UN Convention on the Law of the Sea', 1994, Articles 32, 95, 236.
61. Robin Churchill, 'The Disputed Scope of the Svalbard Treaty Offshore: A New Approach to Resolving the Issue', *Nordic Journal of International Law* (Vol. 91, No. 4, 2022), pp. 544–67; Cecilie Juul Stensrud and Andreas Østhagen, 'Hybrid Warfare at Sea? Russia, Svalbard and the Arctic', *Scandinavian Journal of Military Studies* (Vol. 7, No. 1, 2024), pp. 111–30.
62. Kristian Åtland and Kristin Ven Bruusgaard, 'When Security Speech Acts Misfire: Russia and the *Elektron* Incident', *Security Dialogue* (Vol. 40, No. 3, 2009), pp. 333–53.
63. For example, in 2023, there were reports of fishermen refusing to vacate closed zones in the Barents Sea, similar to another incident in the Irish Sea in 2022. In the latter, local fishermen sailed to an area where Russia had announced plans for naval exercises involving live ammunition. See Thomas Nilsen, 'Defiant Norwegian Fishermen Unwilling to Leave Impact Area of Russian Missiles', *Barents Observer*, 13 August 2023, <<https://thebarentsobserver.com/en/security/2023/08/defiant-norwegian-fishermen-unwilling-leave-impact-area-russian-missiles>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

party, even if the intention is to create a sense of symbolic presence and uncertainty'.⁶⁴ Given the current state of affairs, any accident involving a Russian-flagged vessel bears significant risks for inadvertent escalation.

The potential detrimental effects of these manoeuvres in exacerbating the current tense strategic environment should not be underestimated. Concerns over the activities of Russian fishing vessels fuel a deepening disagreement within NATO about the overall desirability and scope of fishery cooperation with Russia. In July 2023, for example, the UK, Denmark and the Faroe Islands disagreed over whether to continue to grant fishing rights to Russian-flagged vessels in a zone known as 'the Special Area' – where the EEZs of the UK and Faroe Islands overlap. The UK contended that covert activities of the Russian fisheries fleet may constitute a security threat, advocating for the suspension of fisheries. The Danish government, which oversees foreign and defence affairs for the autonomous Faroe Islands, supported this case.⁶⁵ However, the Faroese government, which has autonomous authority over fisheries around the islands asserted that the bilateral fishing agreement with Russia primarily pertained to economic matters.

Consequently, the Faroe Islands declined to terminate the fishing agreement with Russia, placing the central government of Denmark in a challenging position.⁶⁶ Ultimately, the issue was partially resolved through the implementation of port closures for all Russian-flagged vessels unless they are licensed under the fishery agreement.⁶⁷ While the Faroese–Russian fishery agreement was extended into 2024, Russian vessels will not be granted access to fish in the Special Area between the Faroe Islands and the UK.⁶⁸ Russian officials repeatedly argued that these discriminatory measures could lead to the eventual dissolution of the agreement and threatened sanctions on Faroese seafood imports.⁶⁹ Despite the imposed restrictions, the Faroe Islands continue to serve

as a significant hub for Russian fishing activities in the North Atlantic.

The Faroese fishery case demonstrates how purported grey-zone activity of the Russian fishing vessels intersects with broader concerns over resource management and environmental security. This ultimately elevates fisheries to a state security concern. Concurrently, Russia propagates a narrative that implies that the security-driven choice of NATO member states to discontinue cooperation with Russia exacerbates militarisation in the Arctic and negatively impacts indigenous communities. This strains Western sensitivity to environmental concerns, particularly in domestic contexts, and underscores the considerable challenge of reconciling geopolitical tensions with the pressing challenge of environmental protection.⁷⁰

Conclusion

While the Russian war against Ukraine demands immediate attention, it is essential not to overlook the persistent threat that Moscow poses in the European High North. A case in point is the activity of Russian fishing vessels in this region. Their behaviour exemplifies the less-explored dimension of Russian strategic deterrence – the coercive employment of non-military means. Arguably, by shadowing NATO member states' naval vessels, Moscow pursues more than spying. It is important to look into the broader implication of such activities. This article does so by presenting an argument that considers the leverage – applied in the grey zone – that is used for coercive signalling.

The plausibly deniable malicious activities of the Russian civilian fishing fleet operationalises uncertainty. Its activities coercively signal and simultaneously assert Russia's deterrent in relation to its strategic claims in the High North against NATO, and exploit vulnerabilities of the Alliance's member states. This approach

64. See Stensrud and Østhagen, 'Hybrid Warfare at Sea?.'

65. Sune Engel Rasmussen, 'How a Tiny Archipelago Gave Russian Ships a Foothold in the Atlantic', *Wall Street Journal*, 21 July 2023.

66. Charles Szumski, 'Faroe Islands Warns Denmark Not to Probe Russian Ships' Presence', *Euractiv*, 25 April 2023, <<https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/news/faroe-islands-warns-denmark-not-to-probe-russian-ships-presence/>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

67. Government of the Faroe Islands, 'Extended Port Closure for Russian Vessels', 7 July 2023, <<https://www.government.fo/en/news/news/extended-port-closure-for-russian-vessels>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

68. Oliver McBride, 'Faroese-Russian Fisheries Agreement: Quota Adjustments for 2024', *Fishing Daily*, 11 December 2023, <<https://thefishingdaily.com/european-fishing-industry-news/faroese-russian-fisheries-agreement-quota-adjustments-for-2024/>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

69. *RIA Novosti*, 'Farery Vzyali Kurs na Diskriminatsiyu Rossiyskikh Rybakov, Zayavil Posol Barbin' ['The Faroe Islands are Targeting Russian Fishermen, Ambassador Barbin Said'], 20 January 2024, <<https://ria.ru/20240120/farery-1922463755.html>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

70. Grace Evans and Andreas Østhagen, 'In Hot Water: Arctic Fisheries as a Proxy for Geopolitical Tensions', *RUSI Commentary*, 11 July 2023, <<https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/hot-water-arctic-fisheries-proxy-geopolitical-tensions>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

points to Russia's recognition of its limited naval capabilities. It also speaks to its adeptness at exploiting permissive maritime environments to counter the NATO coastal states that currently operate and consolidate in the High North. The observation of the covert-to-overt activity of these vessels reveals how Russian political and military leadership signals a threat by introducing strategic ambiguity, and by operationalising the immediate effects of any below-the-threshold activity to accomplish the country's objectives in advancing its general deterrent posture.

The analysis of how deterrence credibility may be achieved by introduction of grey-zone, non-military activity highlights the complexity of Russia's strategic deterrence concept. It differs from Western approaches in that it blurs the lines between deterrent, dissuasive and compellent elements of deterrence.⁷¹ Moreover, it also contradicts the focus of the Western theoretical conceptualisation of deterrence as immediate. The West's view generally prioritises clear communication of a threat. Instead, by leveraging uncertainty, it attains a certain constraining effect on the adversary by preventing or impeding the adversary's potential retaliatory responses, while asserting one's own interests. In these terms, Russian deterrence strategy seeks long-term effects in shaping the strategic environment in favour of the country's broader political objectives.

Indeed, while Russia's deterrence may often appear opaque or puzzling to observers due to this difference, the restraining effects of these efforts on NATO in the High North are very real.

Indeed, while Russia's deterrence may often appear opaque or puzzling to observers due to this difference, the restraining effects of these efforts on NATO in the High North are very real.⁷² This article contributes to the understanding of non-military means in broadening the understanding of Russian approaches to deterrence. Such understanding precludes the necessity to develop a tailored response to the growing assertiveness of Moscow in the region.⁷³ The Alliance must prioritise dissuasion and denial as guiding principles, demonstrating an understanding of Moscow's signalling and conveying its resolve to respond.

First, this requires an improved capacity for strategic foresight. Recognising the signalling element embedded in Russian grey-zone activities implies the appreciation of the institutionalised use of civilian infrastructure as dual-purpose in Russian statecraft. Such infrastructure includes assets on the seabed, surface and in the airspace. The fishing vessels flying Russian flags and other civilian maritime assets must be included in a shared picture of maritime situational awareness. This suggestion may be considered in the implementation of the NATO Digital Ocean Vision initiative and other similar instruments.⁷⁴ A further development of capabilities and a reassessment of existing national practices are required to adapt the present maritime situational awareness doctrine of Allied Maritime Command to the changing maritime security climate. The Baltic Sentry may set an example of a militarised response to grey-zone challenges to maritime security, but its utility is fundamentally curbed by the real limitations of the naval capabilities of European NATO member states.

Second, the designation of infrastructures as vital, and thus of existential importance, remains an essentially political choice.⁷⁵ On this, it is crucial to recognise fishing as a vital maritime infrastructure, intertwined with shipping and communication facilities.⁷⁶ This opens the possibility for targeted security cooperation with the global fishing industry, as the mutual interest between states and private industries in Europe to protect and preserve sustainable fishing becomes more evident. Furthermore, dialogue is crucial to increase awareness among fishing

71. See Adamsky, 'Deterrence à la Ruse'.

72. Ven Bruusgaard, 'Russian Strategic Deterrence'.

73. See Stensrud and Østhagen, 'Hybrid Warfare at Sea?'.

74. NATO, 'NATO and Industry Work Together to Strengthen Maritime Surveillance', 17 April 2024, <<https://www.nato.int/en/news-and-events/articles/news/2024/04/17/nato-and-industry-work-together-to-strengthen-maritime-surveillance>>, accessed 27 January 2026.

75. Bueger and Liebetrau, 'Critical Maritime Infrastructure Protection'.

76. *Ibid.*

industry representatives about the security and environmental risks posed by Russian fisheries. This awareness will ensure that the industry is 'on board' when further restrictive and law enforcement measures against Russian fishing fleets are considered at the national level.⁷⁷ Moreover, civil–military cooperation could equip the Alliance with additional means to mitigate the disruptive potential posed by Russian dual-use fishing vessels. Recent instances involving the fishing fleets of Ireland and Norway in denying excessive Russian claims for restrictive zones during military exercises offer valuable insights for devising asymmetric approaches to maritime security.⁷⁸

Finally, the foundational work done in recent years to conceptualise deterrence and defence in the cyber domain allows for the further adaptation of approaches to tackle deniable disruptive actions against the security of maritime assets. This adaptation is warranted due to the fundamental similarities between the maritime expanse and the cyber domain. Both domains possess a sovereign-less, transnational character and legal complexity. Additionally, cyber technology plays a critical role in the operation of various types of maritime infrastructure.⁷⁹

Russia's strategic deterrence and its adept operation within the grey zone should serve as a lesson for the West. These seemingly innocuous tactics provide a key to understanding the comprehensive nature of Moscow's contest against the West. The conclusion can only be that NATO must advance the strategic foresight and step up with innovative strategies. This would allow it to further leverage the Alliance's deterrent credibility and the capabilities at its disposal to effectively deny Russia's aggressive assertions in the High North and elsewhere in the North Atlantic. Agility and adaptability are vital for the Alliance to ensure security, stability and adherence to international law across global oceans. ■

Mariia Vladymyrova is ERC-funded 'Ritual Deterrence' PhD fellow at the Department of Political Science, University of Copenhagen. Her dissertation studies Russian approaches to deterrence at sea.

This article is part of the research project funded by the ERC Consolidator Grant Ritual Deterrence, project number 101043468. The views and opinions expressed are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Research Council, and neither can be held responsible for them. The open access publication fee of this article has been covered by the Department of Political Science, University of Copenhagen. This article was first presented at the 2023 UK Deterrence and Assurance Academic Alliance Conference, organised by Dstl and the Scottish Council on Global Affairs, and has undergone several revisions since then. Special thanks to Christian Bueger and Maria Mälksoo for their insightful feedback throughout the drafting process, to Nicholas Taylor for his early appreciation of this idea, and to the reviewers for their constructive comments.

77. Oliver McBride, 'Norwegian Fisheries Group Expresses Concern Over Russian Fishing Practices', *Fishing Daily*, 22 January 2024, <<https://thefishingdaily.com/latest-news/norwegian-fisheries-group-expresses-concern-over-russian-fishing-practices/>>, accessed 26 January 2026.

78. Elisabeth Braw, 'The Fishermen's Revolt Against Russia', CEPA, 18 August 2023, <<https://cepa.org/article/the-fishermens-revolt-against-russia/>>, accessed 26 January 2026.

79. Peter Dombrowski and Chris C Demchak, 'Cyber War, Cybered Conflict, and the Maritime Domain', *Naval War College Review* (Vol. 67, No. 2, 2014).